

Master Teachers' Management Skills

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Abstract:

This study aimed to assess the management skills of Master Teachers in public schools within a medium-sized division in Eastern Visayas during the School Year 2023–2024. Quantitative data were gathered from 329 public school teachers using a validated researcher-made questionnaire. The study focused on management skills in technical assistance, coaching and mentoring, and capability building skills. Profile variables included age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service. Most respondents were younger, female, less tenured, and without postgraduate degrees. Findings revealed that the management skills of Master Teachers were at a high level across all profile groupings. Technical assistance showed no significant difference across variables, while coaching and mentoring, and capability building skills showed significant differences when grouped according to sex. These findings suggest that Master Teachers demonstrate strong management skills.

Keywords: Management Skills, Master Teachers, Technical Assistance Skills, Coaching and Mentoring Skills, Capability Building Skills

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Republic Act (RA) 4670 or the "Magna Carta for Public School Teachers recognizes the need for teachers' advancement and this determines the roadmap for the country's quality education. Executive Order No. 500, series of 1978 paved the way for the creation of the Master Teacher (MT) position through the career progression and promotion program for public school teachers seeking to enhance the effectiveness of classroom teaching.

As an alter ego of the school head, MT's must have the necessary management skills – the ability to communicate well, provide instructions, oversee program implementations and manage the learning community accordingly. The need for Master Teachers to have management skills is not an option but a must according to the Merit Selection Plan as stipulated in the Department of Education's Order No. 29, Series of 2002.

Recent Philippine studies affirm the heightened importance of leadership in education. Torres et al. (2025) conducted a systematic review of school leadership styles in the Philippines from 2015 to 2024. They found that distributed and instructional leadership models, which emphasize teacher development and collaboration, significantly improve teacher performance and school management effectiveness.

The researcher, being a Master Teacher, has personally observed these challenges. Some colleagues are unable to conduct Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions or facilitate mentoring discussions. These gaps raise concerns about the competence of some MTs in delivering their management role. This study, therefore, was conducted to assess the management skills of Master Teachers. Findings aim to inform strategies for improving the management leadership capacity of Master Teachers in public schools.

Current State of Knowledge

Laureano (2023) assessed the mentoring and coaching practices of 493 Master Teachers in the Schools Division of Pangasinan II for SY 2022–2023. Findings revealed that most Master Teachers were in their middle adulthood, female, married, and master's degree holders. Notably, they demonstrated a high level of engagement in mentoring and coaching. However, the extent of their practices varied significantly depending on sex and the number of relevant trainings attended. These results emphasize the importance of continuous professional development to strengthen mentoring effectiveness.

Similarly, in a study conducted in the Dipolog City Division, Dingal (2023) explored the mentoring skills of 27 Master Teachers and their effects on 270 regular teachers and 329 Grade 6 pupils. The study found that Master Teachers' mentoring skills had a very high impact on the instructional practices of teachers and a moderately significant influence on pupils' academic performance. These findings reinforce the idea that skilled mentoring does not only benefit teachers but also contributes meaningfully to student achievement.

In a related context, Gestupa (2023) investigated the instructional supervision and technical assistance provided by Master Teachers in selected public schools in Taguig City and Pateros. The study revealed that while Master Teachers excelled in pedagogical knowledge, content mastery, and mentoring, there were areas needing improvement, particularly in technology integration. Moreover, it was found that demographic factors such as age, sex, and years in service had no significant relationship with the level of assistance they provided. This

suggests that improving instructional leadership may rely more on targeted training than on personal characteristics.

Taken together, these studies highlight the crucial role of Master Teachers in mentoring, instructional support, and school-based leadership. As Gestupa (2023) emphasized, the effectiveness of Master Teachers in providing instructional supervision and technical assistance directly contributes to overall instructional quality. Therefore, sustained capacity-building initiatives and continuous leadership development programs are essential to equip Master Teachers in fulfilling their evolving roles in the education system.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded in the Administrative Management Theory of Henry Fayol (1916), which serves as its foundational framework. Fayol's theory emphasizes the essential functions of management—planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and controlling—as critical components in ensuring organizational efficiency and effectiveness.

Fayol's principles underscore the role of individuals actively engaged in daily operations, drawing from their experiences to refine practices and support others within the organization. This perspective is particularly relevant in the context of education, where leadership and collaboration are central to school improvement.

In the case of Master Teachers, the theory aligns closely with their dual roles as instructional leaders and administrative support to school heads. Beyond classroom instruction, they are expected to manage resources, coordinate professional activities, and provide strategic direction within the learning community.

By applying Fayol's managerial principles, Master Teachers can foster a structured, collaborative, and growth-oriented environment. This, in turn, enhances their capacity to mentor peers, lead professional learning initiatives, and contribute meaningfully to school development and teacher effectiveness.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of management skills of master teachers in public schools within a medium-sized division in Eastern Visayas during the School Year 2023–2024. Specifically, it sought to answer several key questions. First, it examined the profile of the respondents based on age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service. Second, it assessed the level of master teachers' management skills in the areas of technical assistance, coaching and mentoring, and capability building skills. Lastly, the study investigated whether there were significant differences in the level of master teachers' management skills when compared across different respondent profiles.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, data gathering procedure, other instrumentations, and statistical tools. It also discusses the parameters, especially the study's instrument, statistical tools, and the respondents.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to assess the management skills of Master Teachers in a medium-sized division in Eastern Visayas, Philippines, for the School Year 2023–2024. Descriptive research, as defined by Calmorin (2016), focuses on the current situation and seeks to uncover new truths, whether in the form of knowledge, generalizations, or insights. This design was deemed appropriate as it allowed the researcher to observe and describe existing conditions, relationships, opinions, and trends without manipulating the variables involved.

Study Respondents

The study involved 329 public school teachers selected from a total population of 2,265 using stratified random sampling and the Cochran formula to determine the sample size. This sampling method, which divides the population into subgroups or strata based on shared characteristics, ensures proportional representation and enhances the reliability and validity of the research findings (Parsons, 2017). This method also allows for flexibility and ensures that respondents are knowledgeable and experienced in the phenomenon being studied.

Instrument

The study utilized a self-made questionnaire to assess the management skills of Master Teachers, based on the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) by the NEAP and DepEd Region VIII's Regional Order No. 29, s. 2021 on the Learning Achievement via Mentoring Program (LAMP). The instrument had two parts: Part 1 collected demographic data (age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service), while Part 2 focused on management skills with 21 items—seven each for technical assistance, coaching and mentoring, and capability building skills—rated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 5 (Always) to 1 (Almost Never).

Data Gathering and Procedure

After ensuring the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher secured permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and school heads to conduct the study. Hard copies of the approved questionnaire were distributed to the respondents within three days of obtaining the necessary permits, scheduled during lunch breaks (12 noon to 1 pm) to avoid disrupting school activities. After three days, the completed questionnaires were collected for encoding and statistical analysis by a statistician, allowing for computer processing and tabular presentation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 and 2 utilized a descriptive-analytical approach: frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the respondents' profiles; the mean was applied to assess the level of master teachers' management skills across the three areas. Objective 3 employed a comparative-analytical approach using the Mann-Whitney U test to identify significant differences in the management skills of master teachers when grouped and compared according to their profile variables.

Ethical Consideration

Participation in the study was voluntary, with teachers joining based on their own free will. They were fully informed in advance about the study's purpose and procedures. The researcher ensured confidentiality and anonymity of responses, safeguarding participants from any harm. After analysis, raw data was properly destroyed, and all information was used solely for this study.

Results and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to carry out the pre-determined objectives of this study.

Profile of Respondents

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	Younger (below 39 years old)	187	56.80
	Older (39 years old and above)	142	43.20
Sex	Male	90	27.40
	Female	239	72.60
Length of Service	Shorter (below 10 years)	189	57.40
	Longer (10 years and above)	140	42.60
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Bachelor's degree)	241	73.30
	Higher (Master's/Doctorate degrees)	88	26.70
	Total	329	100.0

Table 1 presents a detailed profile of the teacher-respondents, breaking down their characteristics by age, sex, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Most were aged below 35 years (60.90%) and female (68.80%). This points toward an age-advancing and predominantly female teaching population. With regard to civil status, 59.40% were married, while 40.60% were single. On the question of teaching experience, 57.80% had less than 10 years in service, meaning that this might be a fairly young workforce in terms of professional experience. Such characteristics suggest that the respondents are made more or less up of young and early career teachers; hence in their perceptions of academic leadership and professional performance, their adaptability, motivation, and responsiveness to mentoring and leadership schemes may be affected.

Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills

Table 2

Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills in the Area of Technical Assistance Skills

Technical Assistance Skills Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The Master Teacher...</i>		
1. assists teachers to be ready for sudden modality shifting, say face-to-face to virtual, anytime.	4.06	High Level
2. provides constructive and healthy feedback to teachers after each classroom observation (CO).	3.99	High Level
3. encourages teachers to pursue higher education for promotion.	4.08	High Level

4. renders ample time to quality-check modules and other instructional materials.	4.11	High Level
5. assists teachers in achieving effective classroom management.	4.17	High Level
6. trains teachers on how to achieve/provide an effective learning environment for learners.	4.23	High Level
7. shares best practices with other teachers.	3.88	High Level
Overall Mean	4.07	High Level

Table 2 reveals the high level of MT's technical assistance skills.

Item No. 6 which states that "The MT trains teachers on how to achieve/provide an effective learning environment for learners" got the highest mean score of 4.23, interpreted as "high level", while Item No. 2 which states that "The MT provides constructive and healthy feedback to teachers after each classroom observation (CO)" got the lowest mean score of 3.99 interpreted as "high level."

The lowest mean score of 3.99, while still interpreted as a "high level," suggests that there is a need to enhance the quality and effectiveness of the feedback provided by MTs after classroom observations. This may indicate that some teachers feel the feedback could be more constructive, actionable, or timely. There may be few teachers who are not satisfied with the coaching sessions after a CO is conducted.

The findings align with the results of Clariño's (2020) study, which emphasizes the importance of effective instructional support and organizational backing for MTs. Clariño's research indicates that while MTs are viewed as proficient, they often encounter challenges that limit their ability to deliver high-quality feedback, such as heavy workloads and inadequate resources. This suggests that the need for more constructive, actionable, or timely feedback among some teachers may stem from these systemic issues.

Table 3

Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills in the Area of Coaching and Mentoring Skills

Coaching and Mentoring Skills		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The Master Teacher...</i>		
1. evaluates teachers and provides timely feedback to them.	4.36	High Level
2. motivates teachers by identifying their strengths.	3.88	High Level
3. provides positive reinforcement for the identified weakness of teachers.	3.90	High Level
4. conducts FGD regularly to update teachers on issues and classroom matters.	4.05	High Level
5. allows newly hired teachers to do modelling with them for skills development.	3.56	High Level
6. keeps newly hired teachers under their direct supervision for an effective mentoring process.	4.10	High Level
7. always follows a two-way communication system.	4.11	High Level
Overall Mean	3.99	High Level

Table 3 shows that the coaching and mentoring skills of MTs is on high level.

Item No. 1 which states that "MT evaluates teachers and provides timely feedback to them" got the highest mean score of 4.36, interpreted as "high level"; and Item No. 5 which states that "MT allows newly hired teachers to do modelling with them for skills development" got the lowest mean score of 3.56, interpreted as "high level".

This implies that modelling (MT-teacher) must be allowed by the school system considering the fact that some teachers, particularly the newbies, strongly believe this can help them develop their own teaching skills and competencies. However, with the high volume of enrolled students, newly hired teachers are automatically assigned as classroom teachers, therefore, shadowing can be done depending on the existing teaching load of the teachers.

This result is aligned with the study of Sangalang (2018) who investigated the technical support and mentoring abilities of master teachers. The master teachers showed that their general skill level was high, while their specific skill level was also high. Also, the master teachers' degree of technical support for their mentees was high.

Table 4

Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills in the Area of Capability Building Skills

Capability Building Skills		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>The Master Teachers...</i>		
1. teaches younger teachers to be more self-reliant.	4.16	High Level

2. encourages teachers to implement austerity measures in preparing instructional materials amidst budgetary limitations.	4.09	High Level
3. encourages teachers to be fully compliant of all deliverables.	4.31	High Level
4. helps in the formulation of school policies that improve the procurement management system.	4.08	High Level
5. helps in empowering teachers to see their utmost potential as individuals.	4.04	High Level
6. help teachers own or stand up to their decisions based on professional standards.	3.72	High Level
7. Teachers to be more transparent and fairer in all of their dealings with students, parents, and co-teachers.	4.06	High Level
Overall Mean	4.07	High Level

Table 4 reveals the high level of MT’s capability building skills.

Item No. 3 which states that “MTs encourages teachers to be fully compliant of all deliverables” got the highest mean score of 4.31, interpreted as “high level”. Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states that “MTs help teachers own or stand up to their decisions based on professional standards” got the lowest mean score of 3.71, interpreted as “high level”.

Within the bounds of their professional tasks, MTs may only encourage teachers to be more decisive in their undertakings and take responsibility for their actions, because owning one’s decision is a matter personal to an individual. Also, this may suggest that although MTs are generally good at helping teachers, there could be a lack of confidence in their ability to defend their professional or instructional choices in accordance with current standards. This implies that some educators might still mostly rely on supervision and not have complete freedom to follow professional standards on their own.

The results confirm the study of Dingal (2023) which described the mentoring skills of master teachers on teachers’ instructional practices, instructional practices of teachers, and pupils’ academic performance. The mentoring skills of master teachers significantly and highly influence the teachers’ instructional practices. Master teachers who are very highly skilled will enhance the teachers’ instructional practices to be very highly effective. However, the mentoring skills of master teachers along mentoring have a moderate significant effect on pupils’ academic performance.

Comparative Analyses in the Level of Master Teachers’ Management Skills

Table 5

Differences in the Level of Level of Master Teachers’ Management Skills in the Area of Technical Assistance Skills When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	187	165.90	13108.5	0.843	0.843	Not Significant
	Older	142	163.81				
Sex	Male	90	151.48	9538.0	0.112	0.112	Not Significant
	Female	239	170.09				
Length of Service	Shorter	189	163.19	12887.5	0.05	0.687	Not Significant
	Longer	140	167.45				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	241	167.82	9924.5	0.372	0.372	Not Significant
	Higher	88	157.28				

Table 5 summarizes the level of MTs’ management skills particularly in providing teachers with the much-needed technical assistance. From across the four variables, the p-values were all higher than the 0.05 significant level, thus regardless of the respondents’ groupings, there is no significant difference in the level of the said skills. Due to this result, the hypothesis which states that “there is no significant difference in the level of MTs’ management skills in the area of technical assistance skills when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables” is hereby “accepted.”

Clearly, the result implies that the respondents highly believe in the management skills of their master teachers particularly in providing technical assistance skills to all. Almost all of the teachers are in agreement that their MTs are highly skilled in providing technical assistance especially with the newly-hired teachers.

Technical support is provided in accordance with the organization's vision and mission and is determined by its needs. The process of learning is one of cooperation and collaboration. Technical assistance refers to any type of expert assistance, direction, or support that "others" may need to do their duties more successfully. Technical assistance is provided to help with problem solving, performance improvement, obtaining results, and data collection to assist with policy formation (RO). The three most crucial methods of offering technical support are individual coaching, LAC sessions, and classroom monitoring. To fulfill the various requirements of their students, teachers are being enhanced and developed in those three areas where they are poor. The emphasis is more on how regular employees of a school may assist the staff in enhancing student performance and closing the achievement gap.

Finally, the present findings negate the study conducted by Magcanas (2019) which found that the professional growth of teachers is significant when grouped according to some grouping variables.

Table 6
Differences in the Level of Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills in the Area of Coaching and Mentoring Skills When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	187	166.71	12956.5		0.705	Not Significant
	Older	142	162.74				
Sex	Male	90	185.58	8903.0		0.015	Significant
	Female	239	157.25				
Length of Service	Shorter	189	166.56	12936.0	0.05	0.728	Not Significant
	Longer	140	162.90				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	241	166.44	10256.0		0.646	Not Significant
	Higher	88	161.05				

Table 6 reveals the differences in the level of MTs' management skills in the area of coaching and mentoring skills when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

For the variable sex, the p-value is 0.015 which is less than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of MTs' management skills in the area of coaching and mentoring skills when grouped and compared according to sex" is hereby "rejected." As to age, length of service and highest educational attainment, there is no significant difference.

The significant difference when grouped according to sex could be due to gender differences, as male are mostly submissive and non-argumentative compared to the female group. This finding also suggests that male teachers regard MTs'skills in this area more favorably compared to female teachers. This disparity may indicate differing expectations, experiences, or perceptions between the two groups regarding how MTs provide coaching and mentoring. The lower mean rank from female teachers highlights a potential need to explore and address specific concerns or unmet expectations within this group.

This result was supported by the study of Laureano (2023). Results revealed that master teachers surveyed showed a high level of engagement in mentoring and coaching practices. Further, the extent of mentoring and coaching practices of the respondent master teachers differs along sex and number of relevant trainings attended.

Table 7
Differences in the Level of Master Teachers' Management Skills in the Area of Capability Building Skills When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	187	169.13	12505.5		0.365	Not Significant
	Older	142	159.57				
Sex	Male	90	181.74	9248.0	0.05	0.049	Significant
	Female	239	158.69				
Length of Service	Shorter	189	170.31	12226.5		0.238	Not Significant
	Longer	140	157.83				

Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	241	159.13	9190.5	0.063	Not Significant
	Higher	88	181.06			

Table 7 presents the differences in the level of MTs management skills in the area of capability skills when respondents are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Specifically for sex, the p-value was 0.049 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance, thus the hypothesis which states that "there is no significant difference in the level of MTs' management skills in the area of capability building skills when grouped and compared according to sex," is hereby "rejected." As to age, length of service and highest educational attainment, there is no significant difference.

The female group as a relatively low mean score compared to the male group, and the difference could be attributed to the subservient, quiet and non-argumentative character of male teachers. When mentored or coached, they easily agree to instructions and follow to the leader. When there is a disparity in the opinion or male versus female teachers, planned activities and programs may not be easy to implement unless the said differences are properly patched-up. Additionally, the lower mean rank from the female group highlights the need for MTs to ensure that their capability-building strategies are inclusive, responsive, and address the specific needs of all teachers.

The study of Dingal (2023) described the mentoring skills of master teachers on teachers' instructional practices, instructional practices of teachers, and pupils' academic performance. The mentoring skills of master teachers have a very high effect on teachers' instructional practices. Also, it was found out that the level of Master Teachers' management competence in capability building skills has significant difference when grouped according to sex.

Conclusion:

The study established a conclusion that Master Teachers exhibited great levels of management skills in the areas of technical assistance, coaching and mentoring, and capability building skills, due probably to their teaching experience and great interest in the entire school process. Their management attribute was consistently high through variables like age, sex, educational attainments, and years in service, which somehow implies experience and dedication. There is a significant difference in the level of Master Teachers' management skills when grouped according to sex, particularly in the areas of coaching and mentoring skills and capability-building skills, with male teachers giving higher mean ranks compared to female teachers. This indicates that male teachers tend to evaluate Master Teachers more favorably in these areas than their female counterparts do. This finding may imply that male teachers perceive Master Teachers—regardless of the Master Teachers' sex—as more effective in delivering coaching, mentoring, and capacity-building support. It is possible that male teachers are more receptive to the leadership or communication styles commonly exhibited by Master Teachers, or they may engage more frequently in mentoring relationships and technical discussions where those skills are demonstrated. On the other hand, female teachers might hold higher expectations or different standards when evaluating management competencies, which could account for the more moderate ratings. Also, male respondents are more satisfied and can easily follow certain tasks and guidance without being argumentative as oppose to female respondents. These findings emphasize the need for continuous professional development for mentoring to enhance teaching effectiveness across taught career stages.

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